

Entrepreneurship

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Abstract

The primary purpose of this research paper is to understand the importance of entrepreneurship in India. The economic development of the nation depends upon industrial development, and it is based on entrepreneurial skills and competencies of the individuals. Entrepreneurship has to become a popular term currently, but not all of the entrepreneurs can succeed in entrepreneurial business. Entrepreneurial development involves the implementation of various procedures, functions, and activities that are associated with perceiving opportunities and formation of the organizations to pursue them. Entrepreneurs experience several opportunities and challenges within the course of pursuance of their goals and objectives. The main components proposed for inclusion in a definition of the entrepreneur are Innovation, Opportunity Recognition, Risk Management, Action, Use of Resources, Added Value.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, Economic development, Entrepreneurial skills, Entrepreneurial business, Opportunities and challenges, Innovation.

Introduction

Entrepreneurship, among others, as a phenomenon, whose principal required capital is creativity, bravery and using opportunities, is the most important potential source of economic growth, increasing productivity, and producing wealth. In other words, today growth does not rely necessarily on the existence of abundant natural resources or a life of given socio-political system; but depends on human sources

Entrepreneurship is the process of designing, launching, and running a new business, which is often initially small. The people who create these businesses are called entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurship contributes an essential part in the development of the country. The quantity and competence of entrepreneurs affect the economic development of the country. The economic history of the current advanced countries like USA, Russia, and Japan, supports the fact that economic growth is the result for which entrepreneurship is an expected cause.

Entrepreneurship has been described as the “capacity and willingness to develop, organize, and manage a business venture along with any of its risks to make a profit.” While definitions of entrepreneurship typically focus on the launching and running of businesses, due to the high risks associated in launching a start-up, a significant proportion of start-up businesses have to close due to “lack

of funding, bad business decisions, an economic crisis, lack of market demand, or a combination of all of these.”

History of Entrepreneurship

The history of entrepreneurship in India starts in the era of Indus Valley Civilization. Its economy depended majorly on trade, which was facilitated by advanced transportation technology. During the copper age, the Indus Valley Civilization area showed ceramic similarities with southern Turkmenistan and northern Iran, which suggested considerable mobility and trade. During the Early Harappa period (about 3200–2600 BCE), similarities in pottery, ornaments, seals, figurines, etc. document intensive caravan trade with Central Asia and the Iranian country. There was an extensive navigation trade network running between the Harappa and Mesopotamian civilizations as early as the middle Harappa Phase, with much commerce being handled by modern Bahrain and Failaka placed in the Gulf. Such long-distance sea trade became feasible with the innovative improvement of plank-built watercraft, equipped with a single central mast supporting a sail of woven rushes or cloth.

History elucidates that Aside from the subsistence of agriculture and hunting, the Indus people supported themselves by trading goods. Through trade, the Indus Civilization expanded its culture, coming into general contacts with faraway lands.

Need for Entrepreneurship

Every country, whether developed or developing, needs entrepreneurs. Whereas a developing country needs entrepreneurs to initiate the method of development, the developed one needs entrepreneurship to sustain it. In the present Indian context, where on the one hand, employment opportunities in public sector and large-scale sector are shrinking, and on the other, vast opportunities arising from globalization are waiting to be exploited; entrepreneurship can take India to the heights of becoming a super economic power.

Who is an Entrepreneur?

- A person who accepts
- Unreliable risks;
- Fund provider
- Innovative
- Decision maker
- Industrial leader
- Manager or supervisor
- The organizer of economic resources
- Owner of an enterprise
- Employer of production factor
- Contractor
- Arbitrageur
- Allocator of resources among alternative uses
- A person who is aware of the onset of a new business

Types of Entrepreneurship

- Administrative Entrepreneurship
- Opportunistic Entrepreneurship
- Acquisitive Entrepreneurship

- Incubative Entrepreneurship
- Imitative Entrepreneurship
- Private Entrepreneurship
- Public Entrepreneurship
- Individual Entrepreneurship
- Mass Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurship from Schumpeter’s View

In his opinion, a person who creates new business by replacing modern enterprises is not an entrepreneur. According to him, innovations – fulfilling a unique combination – can be classified into five groups:

- Introducing new commodity or a new feature of the merchandise
- Presenting an original method of production
- Opening a new market
- Domination a new source of offering raw material or semi –made commodity
- Creating a new organization of industry.

Process of Entrepreneurship

- Identify an opportunity
- Establishing a vision
- Persuade others
- Gathering resources
- Create a new venture
- Adapt with time

Scope of Entrepreneurship

- The desire for control over one’s future
- More profits
- Lack of employment opportunity
- Government measures to promote entrepreneurship

Women as Entrepreneurs

The development of women entrepreneurs and their involvement in the national economy is quite noticeable in India. The number of women entrepreneurs has developed over some time, especially in the 1990s. Women entrepreneurs need to be acclaimed for their increased utilization of modern technology, increased investments, finding a niche in the export market, forming a considerable occupation for others, and setting the trend for other women entrepreneurs within the organized sector. While women entrepreneurs have validated their potential, the fact remains that they are capable of contributing much more than what they already are. Women’s entrepreneurship needs to be studied individually for two main reasons. The first reason is that women entrepreneurship has been recognized during the last decade as an essential unused source of economic growth.

Women entrepreneurs create new jobs for themselves and others, and also by being different. They provide the society with different solutions, like management, organization, and solutions to business problems, as well as the exploitation of entrepreneurial opportunities. The second reason is that the subject of women in entrepreneurship has been abandoned both, within society in general and in the social sciences. Entrepreneurship amongst women has been a recent concern. Women Entrepreneurs may be defined as women or a group of women who recruit, organize, and operate

a business enterprise. The government of India has defined women entrepreneurs as an enterprise maintained and regulated by a woman having a minimum financial interest of 51 percent of the capital and giving at least 51 percent of employment produced in the enterprise to women. Like a male entrepreneur, a women entrepreneur has many purposes. They should discover the prospects of starting new enterprises, accept risks, the introduction of innovations, direction, management, administration and control of the business, and making provision of effective leadership in all aspects of the company.

Women entrepreneurship is both about women's position in society and about the role of entrepreneurship in the same community. Women entrepreneurs experience many impediments, especially in marketing their products; also, they have to take care of family responsibilities. Women should have access to the same opportunities as men. When they feel they have to perform numerous tasks, they teach the qualities of effective time management, diligence, and resourcefulness. The entry of rural women in micro-enterprises must be strengthened and intensified. Rural women can do wonders by their active and knowledgeable involvement in entrepreneurial activities. The rural women have basic ethnic knowledge, skill, potential, and resources to form and manage the enterprise. Now, the need is for knowledge regarding availability of loans, various funding agencies, procedures regarding certification, awareness on government welfare programs, motivation, technical skill, and support from family and other organizations. Moreover, the formation and reinforcement of rural women entrepreneur's network must be.

Entrepreneurship Training and Education

Michelacci and Schivardi are a pair of researchers who believe that identifying and comparing the relationships between an entrepreneur's earnings and education level would determine the rate and level of success. Their study focused on two education levels, a college degree and a post-graduate degree. While Michelacci and Schivardi do not accurately determine characteristics or traits for successful entrepreneurs, they do believe that there is a primary relationship between education and success, noting that having a college knowledge does contribute to advancement in the workforce.

Michelacci and Schivardi state there has been a rise in the number of self-employed people with a baccalaureate degree. However, their findings also show that those who are independent and possess a graduate degree has remained consistent throughout time at about 33 percent. They briefly consider those famous entrepreneurs like Steve Jobs and Mark Zuckerberg who were college dropouts, but they call these cases all but exceptional as it is a pattern that many entrepreneurs view formal education as costly, mainly because of the time that needs to be spent on it. Michelacci and Schivardi believe that for an individual to reach full success, they need to have education beyond high school. Their research reveals that the higher the education level, the greater the success. The reason is that college gives people further skills that can be used within their business and to operate on a higher level than someone who only "runs" it.

Specific Entrepreneurship Challenges

The various types of challenges that individual experiences in entrepreneurship have been stated as follows:

Family Challenges: The parents who feel that they need the skills and abilities of their children to expand their family business and discourage them from getting engaged in employment opportunities or jobs is stated to be the significant family challenge. It is generally believed by the individuals that are opting for a business rather than an employment opportunity is easy. Well educated and understanding individuals do not want to create strained relationships within their

family. When parents want their children to get involved in the family business, rather than look for a job outside, on the other hand, children do not express willingness to get involved in a family business; then there is an occurrence of a significant family challenge.

Social Challenges: Social challenges are essential in the case of entrepreneurship. There have been instances when individuals undergo the number of problems within the community. If a person is involved in the preparation of food items, which are of good quality, and there is the existence of another entrepreneur, who manufactures the same food items, which are of better quality, then his business will thrive, and there will be more productivity. In this way, productivity and profitability of the entrepreneur decline, when he has a competitor in the market. Therefore, it is understood that social challenges are hard, and individuals need to formulate measures to overcome social problems.

Technological Challenges: In the present existence, technology has gained grounds and contributes an imperative part in the implementation of tasks and operations in all areas. In the field of education, medical, engineering, law, administration, management, science, arts, and so forth, technology is of utmost significance. There are individuals who are not familiar with the usage of technology; they do not feel comfortable with making use of a computer in carrying out various tasks and operations. The technological challenges in the present existence need to be overcome, and individuals, belonging to all categories, occupations, and backgrounds are making use of technologies.

Financial Challenges: Financial challenges are of utmost significance and prove to be the major impediments in carrying out of tasks and functions. In establishing a business, it is necessary to make some investments, and when there is an increase in productivity, then profitability also increases. The individuals who experience financial challenges usually are not able to initiate their business in a worthwhile manner. Most of the non-technical business people do not understand the online business models as a whole and so getting an initial business funding from them becomes challenging. The other option is a loan, but bank loan is not an option in India for new online entrepreneurs.

Policy Challenges: With the changes in the government, there are a lot of changes that have come about in the policies. The significant challenges that entrepreneurs experience are problems in increasing equity capital, issues of availing raw materials, problems of obsolescence of indigenous technology, increase in the pollution that has been ecologically demanding and neglect of small and poverty-stricken countries and so forth. In entrepreneurship, there are specific rules and policies that are put into operation in an effective manner. The entrepreneurs that are poverty-stricken or belong to deprived, marginalized, and socio-economically backward sections of the society, usually experience problems with regards to stringent policies and rules.

Challenges for Rural Entrepreneurs: The significant problems that rural entrepreneurs experience are, growth of mall culture, reduced assistance, power failure, lack of technical knowledge, capacity utilization, and lack of adequate infrastructure. The resources that are necessary to get engaged in a business or entrepreneurship are lacking amongst rural individuals. They are mostly residing in the conditions of poverty and backwardness, possess low levels of literacy, and there is a lack of awareness amongst them. Rearing of livestock, farming, and agriculture are the primary occupations that these individuals get engaged into, to earn their living. They are dependent upon the environmental conditions, water resources, and forests to obtain materials that are necessary for survival.

Opportunities : Free entry into the world trade, improved risk-taking ability, withdrawal of restraints by the Governments of nations, technology and inventions spread into the world, inspiration to innovations and inventions, advancement of healthy completions among nations,

consideration increase in government assistance for international trade, formation of other national and international institutes to support business among countries of the world, assistances of gaining expertise and social and cultural development. The availability of so many opportunities is necessary to help the entrepreneurs be able to achieve their goals and objectives. It is vital on the part of the entrepreneurs to generate awareness, develop practical communication skills, and work towards the achievement of their goals and objectives.

Opportunities for Rural Entrepreneurs: The programs and organizations that generate opportunities for rural entrepreneurs have been stated as follows: Crashed Scheme for Rural Development, Food for Work Programme, National Rural Employment Programme, Regional Rural Development Centres, Entrepreneurship Development Institute of India, Bank of Technology, Rural Innovation Funding and Social Rural Entrepreneurship. In the present existence, the knowledge-based economy is a productive ground for entrepreneurs in India. It is rightly believed that India has an extraordinary availability of capabilities with virtually limitless potential to become entrepreneurs. Therefore, it is essential to become dedicated to generating the right environment to develop efficacious entrepreneurs. To achieve this, India must concentrate on the policies, procedures, rules, and regulations. There should be the availability of prospects for the individuals so that they can develop their entrepreneurship skills and abilities.

Future of Entrepreneurship

Technology plays a crucial role in the future of entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurs can do both strategic planning and administrative work for their business. They can get connected on all surfaces of their business because the Internet makes it possible to do so. The future of entrepreneurship could include high-performing entrepreneurs rather than people working for huge, faceless organizations. The Internet and especially social media tools make it possible to turning passion into a thriving business', and that anyone can create a personal brand and leverage it worldwide through technology.

As the Internet revolution advances, so does entrepreneurship. With always new and more natural ways to build a business, succeeding in this new era is a matter of having two things: the Internet and a device that gives you access to it. Once an entrepreneur has these two, it is a matter of learning and mastering the different tools available online to turn your idea into a thriving business.

Conclusion

"An entrepreneur searches for change, responds to it, and exploits opportunities. Innovation is a specific tool of an entrepreneur; hence, an effective entrepreneur converts a source into a resource."
-Peter Drucker, Management Guru

Entrepreneurship is the lifeblood of any economy. Indian entrepreneurs are more about Overcoming barriers, obstacles, inspiring & surmount in their fields. Entrepreneurship is one of the essential segments of economic growth. Innovation is a critical factor that an entrepreneur brings in an overall change through innovation for the maximum social good. Being an entrepreneur is not just starting a business, it is about having an approach, and one should be motivated to succeed in the achievement of goals and objectives. All successful entrepreneurs have a similar way of thinking and possess several essential personal qualities that make them successful in business. Entrepreneurs need to maintain the required skills and abilities. They should be well prepared to face the opportunities and challenges within the internal and external environmental conditions. In the present existence, entrepreneurship has, to a large extent, contributed towards the economic development of the country and has generated employment opportunities for the number of individuals.

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